

COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES OF WOVEN FABRIC AND/OR GLASS FIBER MAT REINFORCED POLYESTER LAMINATES.

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the laminates moulded from commercial unsaturated polyester resins reinforced by E-glass fibres (continuous and chopped strand mat and plain woven roving fabric), shaped by the hand lay-up and low pressure vacuum injection methods.

The prediction of strength and stiffness, in tension and compression, is analyzed from their components by using some unidirectional and bidirectional models.

This analysis studies the effect caused by the manufacturing process, the number of layers, the reinforcement type and percentage. The location of the fibres inside the matrix is studied by microscopy; finally, mechanical tests, in longitudinal and transverse directions, have been carried out using side support in the compression test. The results have been compared to the predicted values.

1. INTRODUCTION

Predictions of tensile(t)/compressive(c) strength and stiffness are analyzed in surface reinforced laminates from their components using unidirectional models (UD).

The effects caused by the manufacturing process, number of layers, weight, test directions (longitudinal-warp, transverse-weft), type of reinforcement and reinforcement percentage are studied.

Compression is also studied as even when the values obtained are lower than the tensile values, due to sample instability, it does not seem to exist any physical reason for this in glass-fibre composites if initial buckling is avoided. Symmetrical balanced laminae are studied as such laminae prevent flexion-torsion-membrane coupling during the manufacturing process and in structural applications. Structural areas or pieces with improved compressive strength are designed. Although normal working is in tension, pieces or areas working in compression should not be avoided when improvements in the relatively poor stiffness of the composites consisting of curved pieces (shells, arcs), or of straight pieces (open corrugated shapes, tubular panel configurations or sandwich constructions) are to be achieved.

The laminates can also be used in the aircraft or aerospace industry or those areas where no specific design, processing methods or property requirements exist. These laminates are

Figure 1: Micrograph 1. Series 21, Sample of the Injection Point (IP); and Micrograph 2. Series 17, Sample taken far from the Injection Point

formed by commercial unsaturated polyester resins reinforced by E-glass fibre in the form of plain woven roving fabric (WR) (symmetric, balanced and orthotropic) and/or continuous strand mat (CSM) or chopped strand mat (cSM) (both isotropic), moulded by the hand lay-up and low pressure vacuum injection (vRTM) methods, curing being done at room temperature and pressure.

For the hand lay-up method an unsaturated polyester resin ESTRATIL AL-100 dissolved in 33% styrene with 1% Methyl Ethyl Ketona Peroxide (MEKP) as a catalyzer has been used.

Cronolita 10802 with 42% styrene, 2% MEKP as a catalyzer and 0.3% cobalt octoate at 6% as an accelerator is used in the process of injection.

The static testing methods used are based on stiffness and strength measurements under tensile and compressive loads in the weft and warp test directions, at room pressure and moisture. Experimental and predicted values are compared to show the influence of some variables on the final results.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Test panels manufactured using the hand lay-up and low pressure vacuum injection methods were analyzed, both in the warp and in the weft directions. For injection panels, warp direction samples were taken at the point where the injection point (IP) was placed, analyzing the variation in the properties as we moved far away from that point. Table 1 shows the number of layers, type of reinforcement and weight, laminated symmetrically, as well as the mean percentage of fibres obtained for each set of samples (5 units).

Micrographic analysis through sample thickness measures fibre undulation in the matrix, verifying that no fibre displacement occurred during the injection process, and paying special attention to the injection areas. Some micrographs are shown here below in figures 1 and 2.

If we assume that undulation is regular and sinusoidal, the curve length s and the maximum angle are expressed as:

$$y = a \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\lambda}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{s}{\lambda} = 1 + 2\frac{k^2}{8} + 13\left(\frac{k^2}{8}\right)^2 + 90\left(\frac{k^2}{8}\right)^3 + \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\theta_{max} = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{2\pi a}{\lambda}\right) ; k^2 = \frac{c}{1+c} ; c = \left(\frac{2\pi a}{\lambda}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Manufacturing Process	Series	Identification	Tension			Compression	
			set: warp	set: weft	IP	set: warp	set: weft
Hand lay-up	1	6WR275	32.9	33.5		33.2	32.8
	2	8WR275	33.9	33.7		33.9	33.5
	3	10WR275	32.3	32.6		32.9	33.0
	4	2WR800	38.5	38.0		37.4	37.6
	5	3WR800	38.6	37.8		37.2	38.7
	6	4WR800	37.0	35.9		37.6	37.4
	7	3WR800+2cSM450	37.9	36.1		37.3	37.7
Vacuum RTM	8	3WR800+2cSM450	25.5	24.0	21.2	24.7	24.8
	9	3WR800+2CSM450	22.5	24.7	21.2	24.5	26.3
	10	8WR275	21.3	21.8	23.7	22.2	21.9
	11	10WR275	24.7	26.7	32.6	27.3	30.6
	12	12WR275	29.6	28.8	28.1	29.4	30.0
	13	3WR800	26.2	26.2	26.7	26.4	25.3
	14	4WR800	31.0	31.0	28.9	30.8	30.1
	15	5WR800	32.2	31.6	28.3	32.5	31.0
	16	3WR275+2CSM375	12.3	13.2	10.9	12.2	13.3
	17	4WR275+3CSM375	17.2	18.1	15.1	16.6	16.6
	18	5WR275+4CSM375	21.2	22.3	19.7	21.8	21.8
	19	5CSM375+4WR275	20.8	19.8	18.3	20.1	20.8
	20	4CSM375	10.9	10.6	8.2	10.5	9.9
	21	6CSM375	13.8	13.5	11.1	13.0	13.3

Table 1: Identification of the Series and Fibre Content in the Sets (% Vol)

Figure 2: Other Micrographs. Samples of Series 9 and 18.

Weight	Samples	$\frac{a}{\lambda}$	$\frac{g}{\lambda}$	θ_{max}
275 gr/m ²	All	0.0217	1.0046	7.766
	Warp	0.0218	1.0047	7.807
	Warp Hand Lay-up	0.0240	1.0057	8.568
	Warp vRTM	0.0208	1.0043	7.450
	Warp WR+CSM	0.0208	1.0043	7.450
	Weft	0.0223	1.0049	7.970
	Weft Hand Lay-up	0.0295	1.0086	10.507
	Weft vRTM	0.0198	1.0037	7.097
	Weft WR+CSM	0.0198	1.0039	7.097
800 gr/m ²	All	0.0265	1.0069	9.449
	Warp	0.0253	1.0063	9.038
	Warp Hand Lay-up	0.0233	1.0053	8.323
	Warp vRTM	0.0263	1.0068	9.382
	Warp WR+CSM	0.0238	1.0056	8.512
	Weft	0.0278	1.0076	9.906
	Weft Hand Lay-up	0.0285	1.0080	10.158
	Weft vRTM	0.0273	1.0073	9.730
	Weft WR+CSM	0.0270	1.0072	9.632

Table 2: Undulation Description

with the mean values shown in table 2 for the different sets of samples.

Both compression and tensile tests were carried out in a testing bench INSTRON, with two channel graphic output, digital reading and electro-mechanical extensometer, obtaining a strain-stress diagram.

For the compression test a side-support device was adapted to avoid buckling and to let the sample slide under loads. This device was designed by Grimes et al (SWRI), and it is considered to be adequate by Piggot in the case of surface reinforcement. [1][2].

The following graphs (fig. 3, 4 and 5) show the mean values of the elastic moduli (0.1% strain), maximum stresses and strain obtained.

3. PREDICTION

For UD prediction from the properties of the components (matrix and fibres), the following micromechanic equations are used:

Longitudinal elastic modulus and the highest Poisson's ratio: the rule of mixtures.

Transverse elastic modulus: modified rule of mixtures heaving into account Poisson's ratio of the matrix, several empirical pseudo-mixtures and specially Chamis, Puck, Föster-Knoppe, Halpin-Tsai and Tsai-Hahn equations, analyzing the stress partitioning parametres $\mu_T(t, c)$, depending on fibre content, and their effect on the modulus. [3].

The properties of surface reinforced laminates as fabrics can be obtained by using layer models with or without fibre undulation, developed by Piggot, Kabelka, Chou, Ishikawa, et al.

Figure 3: Elastic Moduli.

The base layer can be substituted either for a three-layered lamina, a pure matrix and two layers (one with weft strand and the other with warp strand), or for two layers ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) each one formed by UD laminae. The properties are expressed by the total mean value of the elastic constants of the undulated strand in a representative structural element, with a mean reduction coefficient of 0.94 for the elastic moduli.

In WR composites Poisson's ratios are low and the elastic moduli in the main direction can be obtained as the mean value of the longitudinal and transverse moduli.

If reinforcement is done with cSM or CSM, the modulus can be obtained by calculating its integral in all possible directions; a different possibility could be to obtain the properties of the quasi-isotropic equivalent laminate ($0^\circ/+60^\circ/-60^\circ$) after UD prediction.

Some authors propose simplified versions from UD transverse and longitudinal moduli, or from those of fibres and matrix and fibre percentage.

If the laminate contains the two types of reinforcement a multi-layer model (with orthotropic or isotropic layers, with a thickness proportional to fabric or mat weight) is developed.

In the prediction model an elastic modulus of 73000 *GPa* has been adopted for fibres and 3500 *GPa* for matrix. Poisson's ratios have been 0.25 and 0.35, respectively.

Maximum stresses are predicted, having into account the actual fibre and matrix stresses which are compatible with the strain observed, using the rule of mixtures.

In the tensile test, the elongation due to fibre straightening has been discounted to the measured elongation. A good matching has been obtained when the stress chosen corresponds to the real elongation of the sample. It was thought not to be necessary to use criteria like Hill, Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, etc..

In the compression none of the predictions offered by Rossen, Piggot, Tsai, Steif, Chang,

Figure 4: Ultimate Strength.

Figure 5: Elongation at Break (%).

were useful in our tests; therefore, we adopted Adams, Helminiak and Kumar approach for obtaining the strength from the elastic modulus of the fibres and matrix and from sample strain. It has also been verified that matching from the predicted elastic modulus of the laminate and from sample strain compares well with the results obtained in the tests. [4][5].

Maximum stress values are 1200 MPa for fibres and 45 MPa for resins using the warp tensile test as base deformation. It has been preferred to use always the same values although this causes inappropriate matching in some sets, but it allows us to compare them.

4. RESULTS

The values obtained in the tests (E, S) are normalized with regard to the predicted values (E_i, S_i) depending on the type of reinforcement used (WR and/or cSM or CSM) and their percentage. Changes in the properties are obtained based on test directions, test methods (t,c), manufacturing process, number of layers, weight, different configurations, etc...

In the predictions tested, it has been necessary to choose the UD transverse elastic modulus. For fabric laminates, Halpin-Tsai with $\epsilon = 2$, Chamis, Tsai-Hahn with $\mu = 0.35$ (unundulated) or Tsai-Hahn with $\mu = 0.25$ (undulated) does not affect the final result of prediction and fits well, mainly in tensile tests; Puck, Förster-Knoppe, (unundulated) are close to the previous results; the rule of mixtures and its modification give poor fitting values. Tsai-Hahn with $\mu = 0.2$ (unundulated) fits well in compression.

The following graphs, figures 6 and 7, represent the normalized values of the elastic moduli and strength (Halpin-Tsai, $\epsilon = 0.2$, two layers unundulated) by grouping the samples into sets, showing the mean values and studying the tendencies obtained by linear fitting.

Figure 6: Normalized elastic moduli.

Figure 7: Normalized strength.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In general (see graphs) the behaviour of the normalized moduli, when the fibre content increases, is rather stable with smoothly decreasing values at high weights; the results obtained in compression are higher than expected.

Manufacturing by the injection method also gives a stable behaviour in the normalized moduli; something that does not happen in the hand lay-up method. The moduli and the tendency improve with the number of layers, both in compression and in tension.

Normalized maximum stresses show increasing values in tension and decreasing values in compression, increasing with the number of layers.

CSM-WR composites with a low fibre content present a higher strength in compression than expected, similar to what happens with composites manufactured by the injection method. Samples with low-medium fibre content, low weight, usually manufactured by the injection method, or CSM and CSM-WR, even exceed tensile strength properties with no displacement of the fibres in the injection process.

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